

ISic1066

I.Sicily inscription 1066

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (local)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 64

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140546

1. ὑπατία Ὀνωρίω
2. τὸ □ δ' □ καὶ Εὐτυχιανῶ
3. ἐτελεύτησεν
4. Εὐσκίος μηνὶ Ἰανο-
5. υαρίω ἀπὸ κ (α) □ λ (ανδῶν) □ ια' □
6. □
- 7.

Edition: PHI331914

1. ὑπατία Ὀνωρίω
2. τὸ □ δ' □ καὶ Εὐτυχιανῶ
3. ἐτελεύτησεν
4. Εὐσκίος μηνὶ Ἰανο-
5. υαρίω ἀπὸ κ (α) □ λ (ανδῶν) □ ια' □
6. ὑπατία □ [— — —]AB
7. [— — —]NΠ [— — — —]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492693

EDCS 39102221

PHI 140546

PHI 331914

Bibliography

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